

RECENT AND POTENTIAL CHANGES TO THE U.S. EMC REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, the Federal Communications Commission has made a number of substantial changes to its Rules for controlling unwanted radio frequency (RF) emissions from electronic apparatus to protect radio communications in the U.S.A. The most notable change has been the adoption and use of the international standard CISPR Publication 22 for computers and similar Information Technology Equipment. Because of the trend towards globalization of markets, the FCC is considering additional changes to its Rules, particularly in the area of Conformity Assessment. An update of the FCC Rules and some insights of staff thinking for proposed changes to the Rules will be discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

The Congress of the United States of America in the Communications Act of 1934, as amended, established the Federal Communications Commission and assigned to it the responsibility of developing and promoting radio communications in the U.S.A. in the public interest. As part of that responsibility, the FCC has developed technical and administrative requirements for ensuring the electromagnetic compatibility of electrical and electronic apparatus with radio communication services.¹ Compliance with these requirements is a prerequisite for legal importation and marketing of such apparatus in the U.S.A.² The technical requirements for limiting unwanted RF emissions from unintentional radiators, such as computers, video cassette recorders, microwave ovens, etc., are contained in Parts 15 and 18 of the FCC Rules.³ With the exception of recently adopted rules for cable terminal devices, there are no FCC requirements for controlling the susceptibility of a product. The administrative requirements for such apparatus are contained in Part 2 of the FCC Rules.⁴

FCC RULES FOR DIGITAL DEVICES

In the 1970's, it became clear that computers and data processing equipment were becoming a major source of harmful interference to radio communications in the U.S.A. For this reason, the FCC amended Part 15 in 1980 by adding new standards and administrative requirements for what at the time was defined as computing devices. The name was later changed to digital devices in 1989. The new Rules required computers and similar equipment to meet line conducted and radiated RF emission limits as well as be labelled as complying with the new FCC Rules. The following provides a list of key definitions which are necessary to understand the Rules, examples of typical products and applicable FCC Rule parts:

Intentional Radiator -- A device that intentionally generates and emits radio frequency energy. Examples include low power transmitters operating under the provisions of Part 15 without an individual license, such as cordless telephones, garage door openers, intrusion detectors, remote control and security transmitters.

Unintentional Radiator -- A device that intentionally generates and uses radio frequency energy within the device. The RF energy is not intended to be radiated from the device. Examples include digital devices (ITE), video cassette recorders, radio receivers and similar devices.

Digital Device -- An unintentional radiator that generates and uses timing signals and pulses at a rate in excess of 9,000 pulses (cycles) per second and uses digital techniques. This includes computers, data processing equipment and other types of information technology equipment. The following class of devices are temporarily exempt from the technical and administrative requirements of the FCC Rules:

1. Digital devices in transportation vehicles
2. Digital devices in an industrial plant or public utility facility
3. Test equipment
4. Specialized medical test equipment
5. Digital devices with a power consumption of less than 6 nW
6. Passive devices (e.g., joystick) attached to a computer
7. Battery operated digital devices generating a frequency less than 1.705 MHz.

Personal Computer -- a digital device intended for use in the home or office as personal apparatus for word processing, computations, spreadsheets, database management, games and similar applications. It is inclusive of associated peripherals and I/O devices, e.g. printer, monitor, keyboard, etc.

Information Technology Equipment -- a term used in CISPR Publication 22 to include any equipment that has a primary function of entry, storage, display, retrieval, transmission, processing, switching or control of data or telecommunication messages. It includes data processing equipment, office machines, electronic business and telecommunication equipment.

Class A Digital Device -- A device that is marketed for use in a commercial, industrial or business environment, exclusive of a device which is marketed for use in the home or by the general public.

Class B Digital Device -- A digital device that is marketed for use in a residential environment, notwithstanding use in a commercial, business or industrial environment. The limits for Class B devices are approximately 10 dB tighter than the Class A devices, because of the proliferation and proximity of consumer devices to susceptible receivers.

Most digital devices are self-verified and labelled by the manufacturer.⁵ Only personal computers and associated peripherals are subject to certification by the FCC.⁶

CISPR PUBLICATION 22

On 17 September 1993, the FCC modified Part 15 by allowing manufacturers of digital devices the option

of using either CISPR Publication 22 or the technical standards in Part 15 to demonstrate compliance with Part 15.⁷ There are several important caveats to this option which will be explained below. First, however, it might be helpful to the reader to know a few things about CISPR-22. CISPR is a French acronym for the International Special Committee on Radio Interference. It is a voluntary standards making organization of the International Electrotechnical Committee (IEC). CISPR recommendations, which are voted on by National Committees of the IEC, are voluntary international standards. However, a number of administrations are adopting CISPR recommendations as mandatory standards for controlling interference to radio communications. An example of this process is CISPR-22, entitled: "Limits and methods of measurement of radio disturbance characteristics of information technology equipment." The Commission of the European Union, representing twelve and potentially more member states, is in the process of incorporating this and other IEC standards, into the EMC Directive for products marketed in Europe. Other countries are also considering the adoption of CISPR standards into their mandatory radio regulatory requirements. The first edition of CISPR-22 was released in 1985. The second edition of CISPR-22 was released in December 1993. When the FCC started permitting the use of the international standard, the reference was made to the six CISPR Central Office documents which contained the contents of CISPR-22 (1992).⁸

While the technical standards in Part 15 are very similar to CISPR-22 (1993), there are a number of differences that should be noted, besides the obvious slight difference in the limits. A comparison of the limits is provided in Tables 1 - 4, below. There are also a number of conditions that the FCC placed on the use of CISPR-22 (1993). First, manufacturers must choose between CISPR-22 and Part 15, but cannot use a combination of both standards. Manufacturers who use CISPR-22 must use the measurement procedure C63.4, which in effect gives more detail than CISPR-22.⁹ CISPR-22 is in the process of change, so in the future we expect reference to C63.4 may not be necessary. The tests for line conducted measurements only should also show compliance with the US voltages of 110V/60 cycles. For digital devices with oscillators above 108 MHz, measurements must also be made on frequencies above 1000 MHz, using an instrument with a peak and average detector.

Table 1 -- Comparison of Class A conducted emission limits

Frequency (MHz)	FCC Limits (dB μ V) ¹⁰		CISPR Limits (dB μ V)	
	Quasi-Peak	Average	Quasi-Peak	Average
0.15 - 0.45	None	None	79	66
0.45 - 0.5	60	None	79	66
0.5 - 1.705	60	None	73	60
1.705 - 30	69.5	None	73	60

Table 2 -- Comparison of Class B conducted emission limits

Frequency (MHz)	FCC Limits (dB μ V) ¹⁰		CISPR Limits (dB μ V)	
	Quasi-Peak	Average	Quasi-Peak	Average
0.15 - 0.45	None	None	66 - 56 ¹¹	56 - 46 ¹¹
0.45 - 0.5	48	None	66 - 56 ¹¹	56 - 46 ¹¹
0.5 - 5	48	None	56	46
5 - 30	48	None	60	50

Table 3 -- Comparison of Class A radiated emissions limits

Frequency (MHz)	FCC Limits ¹²	CISPR Limits ¹²
	dB μ V/m @ 10 m	dB μ V/m @ 10 m
30 - 88	39	40
88 - 216	43.5	40
216 - 230	46.4	40
230 - 960	46.4	47
960 - 1000	49.5	47
above 1000	49.5	None

Table 4 -- Comparison of Class B radiated emissions limits

Frequency (MHz)	FCC Limits	CISPR Limits
	dB μ V/m @ 3m (10m) ¹³	dB μ V/m @ 10 m ¹⁴
30 - 88	40 (29.5)	30
88 - 216	43.5 (33.1)	30
216 - 230	46 (35.6)	30
230 - 960	46 (35.6)	37
960 - 1000	54 (43.5)	37
above 1000	54 (43.5)	None

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

As noted above, the FCC is beginning to use, to the extent possible, both U.S. and International standards for regulating EMC. Standard making committees, such as the American National Standards on EMC, C-63, and the IEC/CISPR have the decided advantage of having industry and government representatives develop a consensus standard for handling a particular problem. Consensus standards allow for the sorting out of technical issues and for a smoother transition to either voluntary or, if necessary, mandatory standards. It is also noted that several international agreements, such as the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade and others, are calling for use of international standards, when feasible, to promote trade. These agreements also have language to harmonize conformity assessment issues, so that regardless of the standards, the approval process can be expedited to facilitate trade. A number of U.S. industry groups have expressed interest in harmonizing standards and approval processes, where feasible, to save both time and money in getting products to world markets. For these reasons, the FCC staff has been reviewing the current standards and approval processes in the hope of streamlining the requirements and processes. Questions are being asked to aid in the development of a staff recommendation, for example: Is the present FCC equipment authorization program adequate for protecting radio communications in the U.S.A.? Or, should we consider changes to the program in light of recent international developments? What should those changes entail? Should we consider the European approach of giving laboratories that meet certain competency requirements greater flexibility? Should we consider the European approach of manufacturer self-approval for most equipment, e.g. personal computers? Answers to questions like these will help the staff in developing a recommendation in the form of a Notice of Proposed Rule Making and/or Notice of Inquiry. The Proposal/Inquiry, which will solicit comments from interested parties, is expected to be ready for consideration by the Commission and released by late 1994 or early 1995.

One final comment. The opinions expressed in this paper are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the opinions of the Commission or the staff.

ENDNOTES

1. Section 302 of the Communications Act of 1934, as amended, gives the FCC authority to regulate any device which in its operation is capable of causing harmful interference to radio communications. The FCC also has authority to regulate the immunity of home entertainment products. This authority may be applied to manufacture, importation, shipment, sale, offer for sale, lease, etc. of such devices (47 U.S.C. 302).
2. The importation and marketing of devices subject to FCC Rules are contained in Section 2.801 *et seq.* (47 CFR 2.801).
3. The Rules for intentional and unintentional radiators are contained in Part 15 of the FCC Rules (47 CFR Part 15). The Rules for controlling interference from Industrial, Scientific and Medical Equipment are contained in Part 18 (47 CFR Part 18).
4. The requirement for an equipment authorization is contained in the FCC Rule Part for the particular device (e.g. Part 15). The procedure for obtaining the equipment authorization is contained in Subpart J of Part 2 of the FCC Rules (47 CFR 2.901 *et seq.*).
5. Most digital devices are subject to verification by the manufacturer, which is an equipment authorization process whereby the manufacturer tests for compliance, provides information to the user and labels the equipment with the statement required by 47 CFR 15.19. See 47 CFR 2.901 *et seq.* for more details about the verification program.
6. Certification is a bilateral equipment authorization required by the FCC for those equipment which are deemed to have a significant potential for causing radio interference. For equipment subject to certification (e.g., personal computers), the manufacturer must test his equipment for compliance and send a copy of the report of measurements, application, application fee, description of equipment, photographs, etc. to the FCC for review and approval. The equipment must also be labelled. The FCC review process takes on the average about 30 days. The administrative Rules are contained in 47 CFR 2.901 *et seq.*

7. Part 15 was amended in the Report and Order in FCC ET Docket No. 92-152, entitled "In the matter of revision of Part 15 of the Rules to harmonize the standards for digital devices with the international standards", adopted 20 August 1993, and released 17 September 1993. The Rules became effective upon publication in the U.S. Federal Register.

8. At the time Part 15 was amended, the second edition of CISPR-22 was not available. So as not to delay use of the international standard, the FCC referenced the following six documents which amended the first edition: CISPR/G (Central Office) 2, CISPR/G (Central Office) 9, CISPR/G (Central Office) 11, CISPR/G (Central Office) 12, CISPR/G (Central Office) 13, and CISPR/G (Central Office) 14. The FCC Chief Engineer has been given the delegated authority to substitute CISPR-22 (1993) for the six documents and make other non-controversial changes to the Rules.

9. ANSI Standard C63.4-1992 is entitled: American National Standard for Methods of Measurement of Radio Noise Emissions from Low-voltage Electrical and Electronic Equipment in the Range of 9 kHz to 40 GHz. It is available from the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc., Service Center, 445 Hoes Lane, P.O. Box 1331, Piscataway, NJ , 08855-1331, U.S.A., Facsimile No. 1-908-981-9667, Telephone No. 1-908-981-1393.

10. These tables are based on a comparison between the FCC Rules, Part 15, and CISPR Publication 22, Second Edition (1993). A comparison of the FCC and CISPR conducted limits must take into account the differences in measurement procedures. While the FCC does not have a limit on the average value of

conducted emissions, the measurement procedure permits the 13 dB to be subtracted from the quasi-peak measured values if the difference between the quasi-peak and average measured values is 6 dB or greater. Under this condition, the limit for Class B digital devices becomes 61 dB μ V (q-p) and 55 dB μ V (average), representing the minimum 6 dB difference. Similarly, for a Class A device the limits become 73 dB μ V(q-p) and 67 dB μ V(average) for the band 0.45 - 1.705 MHz and 82.5 dB μ V(q-p) and 76.5 dB μ V (average) for the band 1.705 - 30 MHz.

11. This limit decreases linearly with the logarithm of the frequency.

12. Both the FCC and CISPR limits below 100 MHz are based on q-p measurements. FCC measurements above 1000 MHz are based on the use of an average detector with a peak limitation of 20 dB above the average value. Measurements above 1 GHz are required under 47 CFR 15.33.

13. The FCC Class B limits were converted to limits at 10 meters using a far field inverse linear distance extrapolation factor. The number in () is the extrapolated limit at 10 m.

14. CISPR Publication 22 states that if the field strength measurement at 10 meters cannot be made because of high ambient noise levels or for other reasons, measurements may be made at a closer distance, e.g. 3 meters. An inverse proportionality factor of 20 dB per decade should be used to normalize the measured value to the specified distance for determining compliance. Care should be taken in measurement of large test units at 3 meters at frequencies near 30 MHz due to near field problems.